

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA INTERACCION Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 16 No. 2
Mayo - Agosto
2026

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

INTERACCIÓN Y PERSPECTIVA

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X ~ Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19243090>

Vol. 16 (2): 454 - 473 pp, 2026

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

La percepción de los valores familiares por parte de los jóvenes en un entorno social cambiante*

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Resumen. La investigación se centró en jóvenes que se adaptan a nuevos contextos culturales o regionales. El método principal empleado fue una encuesta. Los resultados muestran que el amor, la comprensión mutua, el respeto y el apoyo siguen siendo valores familiares fundamentales, mientras que el cambio social y la globalización se perciben como influencias importantes. Surgieron diferencias de género: las mujeres dieron mayor importancia a la cercanía emocional, mientras que los hombres tendieron a priorizar la estabilidad financiera y la independencia. A pesar de los indicios de una creciente autonomía, se preservaron la comunicación regular y los vínculos afectivos con la familia, lo que indica que los valores fundamentales mantienen su relevancia incluso cuando los estudiantes se enfrentan a desafíos de adaptación en nuevos entornos. El análisis estadístico reveló una correlación moderada entre el género y la orientación de valores (V de Cramer = 0,63), lo que confirma que las expectativas de género siguen moldeando la percepción de los roles familiares. Los hallazgos

*The article was made within the framework of a grant for the implementation of fundamental and applied scientific work in scientific and educational organizations, enterprises and organizations of the real sector of the economy of the Republic of Tatarstan of the Russian Federation with the support of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan of the Russian Federation (agreement No. 22/2024-FIP of 25.12.2024).

sugieren que, si bien los valores tradicionales siguen siendo importantes, los jóvenes los reinterpretan en el contexto de la vida digital, la migración y la evolución de los roles de género. Estas reinterpretaciones demuestran una flexibilidad para equilibrar las normas culturales heredadas con las realidades sociales contemporáneas. El estudio subraya la necesidad de entornos educativos y sociales que apoyen la continuidad cultural, al tiempo que abordan los desafíos de un mundo en constante cambio y fomentan la formación de valores saludables entre los jóvenes.

Palabras clave: valores familiares, percepciones juveniles, cambio social, diferencias de género, disonancia cognitiva.

The perception of family values by young people in a changing social environment

Abstract. In modern society, the formation of traditional family values among young people is becoming increasingly important. This study explores how young people perceive traditional family values amid ongoing social change. The research focused on young people adapting to new cultural or regional contexts, such as relocation for higher education. A survey was conducted among 50 participants at the Elabuga Institute of Kazan Federal University, equally divided between local residents and those from the Luhansk People's Republic. The results show that love, mutual understanding, respect, and support remain central family values, while social change and globalization are viewed as major influences. Gender differences emerged: women placed more emphasis on emotional closeness, while men tended to prioritize financial stability and independence. Despite signs of growing autonomy, regular communication and emotional bonds with family were preserved, indicating that core values maintain their significance even when students face adaptation challenges in new environments. Statistical analysis revealed a moderate connection between gender and value orientation (Cramer's $V = 0.63$), confirming that gender-linked expectations continue to shape perceptions of family roles. The findings suggest that while traditional values remain important, young people reinterpret them in the context of digital life, migration, and evolving gender roles. These reinterpretations demonstrate a flexible approach to balancing inherited cultural norms with contemporary social realities. Overall, the study underscores the need for supportive educational and social environments that respect cultural continuity while addressing the challenges of a rapidly changing world and fostering healthy value formation among young adults.

Key words: family values, youth perceptions, social change, gender differences, cognitive dissonance.

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, there is a radical change in generational paradigms that poses a difficult choice for young people: whether to maintain established values or adapt to new challenges (demographic, ideological, value, identity)? The formulation of this problem allows us to study the perception of traditional values by university students in

the context of the transformation of traditional values. It is the modern youth of 18-25 years old, who found themselves at the “junction of eras”, who are simultaneously the carriers of traditional values and the agents of changes (Gapsalamov et al., 2020; Akhmetshin et al., 2021; Shichkin et al., 2024).

One of the key traditional values for Russian society is undoubtedly the family. A survey by the All-Russian Center for the Study of Public Opinion (VTsIOM) showed that even for the youngest Russians (18-24 years old), family and raising children remain a priority goal in life (74%) (VTsIOM, 2023). Nevertheless, there are many factors that influence the formation of the value attitude of young people towards the family and its traditions. One of these significant factors is the change in the social environment. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the category “student youth of higher education”, especially to those students who, due to certain life circumstances, are forced to change their region of residence to regions with a social environment that is not identical to them. The new social environment calls into question the sustainability of traditions, which leads to a conflict of values among students, especially freshmen.

METHODOLOGY

In the course of this study, we had to identify the perception of traditional family values by students of higher education in the context of a changing social environment based on the factors influencing the formation and change of these values, as well as determine the impact of social transformations on family relationships and students’ expectations.

Research methodology

During the study, we relied on the concept of cognitive dissonance by Leon Festinger (1968), who defined cognitive dissonance as a person’s uncomfortable state resulting from a mismatch between their actions and thoughts. In the theory of cognitive dissonance, Leon Festinger (1968) hypothesized that internal tension (discomfort) is so unpleasant for the psyche that a person seeks to “remove” it by any means, often distorting or correcting his own views, that is, dissonance becomes an inevitable consequence of making a decision (conscious or unconscious).

Research hypothesis

Together, the above provisions made it possible to formulate a study hypothesis about the perception of traditional family values by higher education students in the context of social changes based on cognitive dissonance due to the need to combine conflicting attitudes obtained from different sources (family, university, peers, digital environment). It follows that students’ family values depend on their social environment and cultural traditions, yet students raised in traditional families are more likely to retain traditional family values despite social changes.

Social environment factors influence students’ psychological well-being, academic performance, and social adjustment. In the new social conditions, students are faced with the need to choose between two or more significant, but contradictory values (for example, family vs. career, religion vs. science, etc.). A person is forced to make a choice that contradicts one of the sides

of his personality. This leads to psychological discomfort caused by the contradiction between beliefs, actions and changed circumstances.

Research problems

The proposed hypothesis determines the need to solve the following tasks:

- 1) In the context of social changes, identify the sources of cognitive dissonance among high school students in a new social environment that affects their perception of traditional family values.
- 2) Develop a questionnaire and conduct a survey of higher school students in determining their perception of traditional family values in the context of social changes.
- 3) Analyze the received personal data to find ways to harmonize the adoption of traditional family values by students of higher education in the new social conditions.

Solving the tasks

The indicated tasks were solved during the study as follows. Identification of sources of cognitive dissonance in high school students in a new social environment that affects their perception of traditional family values was carried out on the basis of a theoretical analysis of special scientific literature and statistical studies (Usova et al., 2020; Manukyan, 2022; Gritsenko et al., 2023; Korotaeva et al., 2023; Ali et al., 2024; Gilemkhanova, 2024; Karabanova et al., 2024).

The problem of the current state of the sociocultural environment raises the question of the vector of cultural changes in society. As E.N. Gilemkhanova (2024) notices, trends in civilizational development lead to a revision of basic cultural norms. This trend indicates a change in the perception of traditional family values by modern youth.

One of the powerful trends today is the digitalization of the social environment. Establishing the connection between the basic values of a person and the nature of psychological adaptation to global digital risks was carried out by O.A. Karabanova, O.A. Tikhomandritskaya and S.V. Molchanov (2024), who identified groups differing in the level of psychological adaptation to digitalization, revealed differences in basic beliefs and social beliefs, value orientations in people with different levels of psychological adaptation to digitalization and conducted a comparative study of the age characteristics of psychological adaptation of the personality to digitalization in youth and middle maturity.

However, V.V. Gritsenko, M.Y. Chibisova, N.V. Tkachenko and O.E. Khukhlaev (2023) point to the tendency of young people to integrate into a new social environment, which provides positive relationships between indicators of socio-cultural adaptation and indicators of psychological well-being.

It is worth noting that the preservation of traditional family values is one of the factors for the adaptation of the individual in the new social environment. O.V. Usova, N.G. Chevtaeva, A.S. Nikitina, C. Scavo (2020) describe the phenomenon of social representation of the family through its perception by educators as prosperous or dysfunctional, which is formed as a response to prosocial/deviant behavior demonstrated by students in grades 7-11.

The study by E.V. Korotaeva, A.S. Andryunina and I.G. Chugaeva (2023) proves that the harmonization of family and school relations as a social environment is possible if the development of educational relations is built on the principle of dialogue aimed at bringing together the interests of educational subjects, developing a single educational strategy, common values and goals of education.

Within the framework of the concept of cognitive dissonance, we were interested in the work of V.R. Manukyan (2022), which focuses on the process of growing up of young people during the period of “emerging adulthood” in terms of the course of psychological separation from parents and its relationship with the formation of adult identity (subjective adulthood) and psychological well-being.

Our study also focuses on the perception of traditional family values by high school students based on gender type (male vs. female). This choice is due to the desire to understand how gender interacts with traditional family values in the minds of a key group (high school students) influenced by modern sociocultural trends.

Modern researchers pay great attention to gender issues. In particular, R.A. Saavedra, R. Ranjan, A. Philominraj and C.A.C. Urzua (2024) conduct an analysis of values associated with pedagogical training and differences in value preferences depending on the gender of students at universities in central-southern Chile.

Anticipating a gender future in the lens of young people’s relationship financial habits and their work and family plans are considered by E. Wolfinger, B. Hanckel and K. Huppertz (2025). N. Ali, U. Daraz, M. Ibrahim, M. Hussain, Y. Khan, S Ali (2024) establish the relationship between student’s gender and their family’s socioeconomic status on academic performance. A. Christofidou and G. Zafeiridou (2025) pay attention to such a gender aspect as the analysis of the problem of changing fatherhood and hybrid masculinity in Cyprus, considering modern gender relations and social changes in a unique context between tradition and modernity, while noting how much this context affects the behavior of a man as a man and as a father.

The problem of “positive humanity”, namely the rejection of a fixed gender approach, is reflected in the work of F. Mackay (2025), which argues that this will allow a new look at men as equal, humane, inclusive, positive and healthy people, without the need to constantly single them out as men and male representatives.

In addition, research is currently underway that notes the commitment of women to traditional lifestyles. In particular, R.L. Stotzer and A. Nelson (2024) distinguish three main topics of women’s choice of traditional life, namely, the belief system, practicality and sense of security, as well as the interweaving of themes of isolation and romanticization of lifestyle.

The studies discussed above prompted us to clarify gender differences in the context of the perception of family values by university students in a changing social environment.

In the process of analyzing the problem under study, based on a number of methods proposed in psychological and pedagogical science (Abrahamyan, 2009; Bukhtoyarova et al., 2015; Shcherbina, 2024), the author’s questionnaire “Perception of traditional values by university students in the context of a changing social environment” was developed, in the structure of which factors were identified that affect the formation and change these values as triggers for the

cognitive dissonance of high school students. The questionnaire included questions about family values, family relationships, the impact of social change on family relationships and expectations. The Cramer coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between two categorical variables (by gender) and calculate the similarity of survey data according to the selected statistical criterion in the processing of questionnaire data.

RESULTS

The survey was attended by 50 students of Elabuga Institute of KFU, including 25 respondents – students who arrived from the Luhansk People’s Republic (50%) and 25 respondents – residents of the Republic of Tatarstan (50%). Among the respondents there are 30 female students (60%) and 20 male students (40%). From the personal data, the marital status of the respondents was established. Thus, 90% of respondents (45 people) are “not married”; 10% (5 people) are “legally married”; 10% (5 people) are “in a relationship”, 0% (0 people) are “divorced”.

Table 1 shows the age of the respondents (from 18 to 20 years).

TABLE 1. Age of students participating in the survey.

Age	Absolute value	Percentage
18-20 years	25	50%
21-23 years	20	40%
24-25 years	5	10%

Analysis of the data showed that the sample was dominated by women (60%), which may be due to a higher proportion of women among university students. This can affect perceptions of family values, as women are traditionally more family-oriented.

Most of the respondents are aged 18-20, which corresponds to student age. This may affect their perception of family values, since at this age there is an active formation of life priorities.

Equal distribution between the Republic of Tatarstan and new regions of Russia may indicate a variety of cultural and social influences on the perception of family values of higher education students.

Most respondents are not married, which is typical of student age. This can affect their expectations of future family relationships.

In the section of the questionnaire “Perception of family values”, respondents answered the following questions.

To the question “What family values are most important to you?” The following data were obtained: “love and mutual understanding” – 40 respondents; “respect and support” – 35 respondents; “traditions and cultural values” – 20 respondents; “financial stability” – 15 respondents; “personal space and independence” – 10 respondents; “others” – 5 respondents (Table 2).

TABLE 2. Respondents' answers to the question "What family values are most important to you?"

Family values	Absolute value	Percentage
Love and mutual understanding	40	80%
Respect and support	35	70%
Traditions and cultural values	20	40%
Financial stability	15	30%
Personal space and independence	10	20%
Others	5	10%

From the data presented in Table 2, it can be seen that the majority of respondents note the importance of love and mutual understanding, which reflects the common values inherent in young people. Women are more likely to point out the importance of respect and support, which may be due to their more emotional perception of family relationships.

To the next question "Do you think family values have changed over the past 10 years?" respondents answered: "Yes, they have changed significantly" – 30 respondents; "Yes, but not insignificantly" – 15 respondents; "No, they remained the same" – 5 respondents; "I find it difficult to answer" – 0 respondents (Table 3).

TABLE 3. Respondents' answers to the question "Do you think family values have changed over the past 10 years?"

Changing of family values	Absolute value	Percentage
Yes, changed significantly	30	60%
Yes, but not significantly	15	30%
No, they remained the same	5	10%
I find it difficult to answer	0	0%

As we can see, the majority of respondents believe that family values have changed over the past 10 years. This may be due to social and cultural changes.

Next, the respondents were asked to answer the question "What factors do you think influence the change in family values?". The following answers were received: "social changes and globalization" – 35 respondents; "economic conditions" – 20 respondents; "cultural and religious traditions" – 15 respondents; "education and upbringing" – 10 respondents; "Media and Internet" – 5 respondents; "others" – 5 respondents (Table 4).

TABLE 4. Respondents' answers to the question "What factors do you think influence the change in family values?"

Factors influencing family values	Absolute value	Percentage
Social change and globalization	35	70%
Economic conditions	20	40%
Cultural and religious traditions	15	30%
Education and upbringing	10	20%
Media and Internet	5	10%
Others	5	10%

Responses from respondents in Table 4 indicate that social change and globalization are the major factors influencing family values. Taken together, this reflects the impact of current trends on perceptions of family relationships.

In the "Family Relationships" section of the questionnaire, students answered the questions which results are presented below. To the question "How do you assess the relationship in your family?" the students' choice of answers indicated that "very good" relationships – 20 respondents, "good" – 20 respondents, "satisfactory" – 10 respondents, "bad" – 0 respondents, "very bad" – 0 respondents. The percentages are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5. Respondents' answers to the question "How do you assess the relationship in your family?"

Assessing family relationships	Absolute value	Percentage
Very good	20	40%
Good	20	40%
Satisfactory	10	20%
Bad	0	0%
Very bad	0	0%

Most respondents rate their family relationships as "good" or "very good," which may indicate a positive perception of family relationships.

To the question "How often do you communicate with your family members?" respondents answered: "daily" – 25 respondents; "several times a week" – 15 respondents; "several times a month" – 10 respondents; "rarely" – 0 respondents; "practically do not communicate" – 0 respondents (Table 6).

TABLE 6. Respondents' answers to the question "How often do you communicate with your family members?"

Frequency of communication with family	Absolute value	Percentage
Daily	25	50%
Several times a week	15	30%
Several times a month	10	20%
Seldom	0	0%
Practically do not communicate	0	0%

According to the indicator "Frequency of communication with the family", we see that the majority of respondents communicate with the family daily or several times a week. Student responses point to the importance of family ties.

In order to determine the dynamics of changes in family relationships since the students were in a new social environment, they were asked to answer the question "What changes in family relationships have you noticed in recent years?" As a result, the answers showed that 15 respondents chose "increasing distance and independence"; "increased emotional intimacy" – 20 respondents; "changing roles and responsibilities" – 0 respondents; "decrease in the significance of traditions" – 5 respondents; "others" – 0 respondents (Table 7).

TABLE 7. Respondents' answers to the question "What changes in family relationships have you noticed in recent years?"

Changes in family relationships	Absolute value	Percentage
Increasing distance and independence	15	30%
Increased emotional intimacy	20	40%
Changing roles and responsibilities	10	20%
Decrease in the significance of traditions	5	10%
Others	0	0%

The survey results presented in Table 7, on the one hand, indicate a tendency to distance and independence of young people from their parents, and on the other hand, an increase in emotional intimacy between them. Such an indicator may reflect modern trends in family relationships.

At the next stage of the survey, in the section "Social Changes and Family Values", to the question "Do you think social changes affect family values?" students answered: "Yes, significantly affect" – 35 respondents (70%); "Yes, but insignificant" – 10 respondents (20%); "No, do not affect" – 5 respondents (10%); "I find it difficult to answer" – 0 respondents (0%). Thus, the majority of respondents believe that social changes significantly affect family values. This reflects students' awareness of the influence of external factors on family relationships.

Further in this section, respondents were asked to answer the question “What social changes do you think most strongly affect family values?” The results of the responses to this question are presented in Table 8.

TABLE 8. Respondents’ answers to the question “What social changes do you think most strongly affect family values?”

Social changes	Absolute value	Percentage
Urbanization and migration	20	40%
Changing gender roles	15	30%
Technology and Internet development	10	20%
Changing economic conditions	5	10%
Political changes	0	0%
Others	0	0%

As Table 8 shows, urbanization and migration, as well as changing gender roles, are major social changes affecting family values.

Also during the survey, students expressed their opinion on the impact of modern social changes on family values. The results of the answers to this question are presented in Table 9.

TABLE 9. Respondents’ answers to the question “Do you think modern social changes contribute to the strengthening or destruction of family values?”

The impact of social change on family values	Absolute value	Percentage
To strengthening	20	40%
To destruction	20	40%
Not affected	10	20%
I find it difficult to answer	0	0%

According to respondents, social changes contribute to both the strengthening and destruction of family values, which reflects the ambiguity of their impact on this category of persons.

The next section focused on the role of education and upbringing in shaping traditional family values. Most students (30 respondents – 60%) believe that education and upbringing “Yes, significantly affect” the perception of family values; 15 respondents (30%) chose the answer “Yes, but not significantly”; 5 respondents (10%) – “No, do not affect”; 0 respondents (0%) – “I find it difficult to answer.” Most respondents believe that education and upbringing significantly affect the perception of family values. The opinion of the surveyed students indicates their awareness of the importance of upbringing in the formation of family values.

In choosing the most important aspects of education and upbringing for the formation of family values, students identified: “family education” – 30 respondents (60%); “school education” – 20 respondents (40%); “university education” – 10 respondents (20%); “religious education” – 5 respondents (10%); “cultural education” – 5 respondents (10%); “others” – 0 respon-

dents (0%). According to respondents, family education is a major aspect affecting family values, reflecting the importance of family traditions and values.

The questionnaire also included a section “Personal expectations and plans”, which allows us to determine the attitude of students to the image of their future family and the role of family traditions in it. According to the results of the survey, it turned out that students would like to convey to their children such family values as: “love and mutual understanding” – 30 respondents (60%); “respect and support” – 25 respondents (50%); “traditions and cultural values” – 15 respondents (30%); “financial stability” – 10 respondents (20%); “personal space and independence” – 5 respondents (10%); “others” – 5 respondents (10%). Students project their future family in the image of a “traditional family” (25 respondents – 50%); “modern family with flexible roles” (20 respondents – 40%); “families with a focus on personal freedom” (5 respondents – 10%); “families with a focus on financial stability” (5 respondents – 10%); “other” (5 respondents – 10%). The survey results indicate the desire of the majority of respondents to convey love and mutual understanding to their children, which reflects the common values inherent in young people.

As a result of the survey, students pointed to changes in family relationships that they would like to see in the future. So, 20 respondents (40%) want “more emotional intimacy”; “more financial stability” – 15 respondents (30%); “more respect and support” – 10 respondents (20%); “more personal space” – 5 respondents (10%); “others” – 10 respondents (20%). That is, most respondents see their future family as traditional or modern with flexible roles, which reflect the variety of expectations from family relationships.

At the conclusion of the survey, students were invited to provide comments and/or additional comments on the research topic. The results of the survey are presented in Table 10.

TABLE 10. Comments and/or additional comments on the study topic.

Comments available	Absolute value	Percentage
Yes	10	20%
No	40	80%

Table 10 provides a detailed overview of questionnaire data, including absolute values and percentages for each block of responses.

DISCUSSION

As noted above, in this study we were interested in gender differences in the context of the perception of family values by university students in a changing social environment. According to the results of the survey, the following data were obtained, which demonstrate the perception of family values by university students in the context of a gender change in the social environment.

Table 11 provides an overview of students’ sex differences.

TABLE 11. General information on respondents' sex differences.

Sex	Absolute value	Percentage
Male	20	40%
Female	30	60%

Table 12 provides a gender perspective of respondents on perceptions of family values.

TABLE 12. Comparison of respondents' perceptions of family values according to gender.

Family values	Male	Female
Love and mutual understanding	16 (80%)	24 (80%)
Respect and support	14 (70%)	21 (70%)
Traditions and cultural values	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Financial stability	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
Personal space and independence	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Others	2 (10%)	3 (10%)

The differences between males and females in family relationships are presented in Table 13.

TABLE 13. Comparison of respondents' perceptions of family relationships by gender type.

Assessing family relationships	Male	Female
Very good	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Good	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Satisfactory	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Bad	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Very Bad	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

TABLE 14. Comparison of respondents' perceptions by gender type.

Frequency of communication with family	Male	Female
Daily	10 (50%)	15 (50%)
Several times a week	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
Several times a month	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Seldom	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Practically do not communicate	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

As a follow-up to the analysis of the questionnaire data, the authors also compared respondents' responses by gender type about their vision of social change and the impact of these changes on family values (Table 15, Table 16, Table 17).

TABLE 15. Respondents' perceptions of the impact of social change (by gender type).

The impact of social change	Male	Female
Yes, significantly affect	14 (70%)	21 (70%)
Yes, but not significantly	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
No, do not affect	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
I find it difficult to answer	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

TABLE 16. Respondents' perceptions of social changes (by gender type).

Social changes	Male	Female
Urbanization and migration	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Changing gender roles	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
Technology and Internet development	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Changing economic conditions	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Political changes	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Others	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

TABLE 17. Respondents' perceptions of the impact of social change on family values (by gender type).

The impact of social change on family values	Male	Female
To strengthening	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
To destruction	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Not affected	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
I find it difficult to answer	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

A comparison of the opinions of male and female respondents on the impact of education and upbringing on the formation of family values in the individual is presented below in Table 18.

TABLE 18. Respondents' perceptions of the impact of the impact of education and upbringing (by gender type).

Impact of education and upbringing	Male	Female
Yes, significantly affect	12 (60%)	18 (60%)
Yes, but not significantly	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
No, do not affect	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
I find it difficult to answer	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

TABLE 19. Respondents' perceptions of the impact of the aspects of education and upbringing (by gender type).

Aspects of education and upbringing	Male	Female
Family education	12 (60%)	18 (60%)
School education	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
University education	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Religious education	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Cultural education	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Others	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Below is a comparison of personal expectations and plans of male and female respondents according to their sex (Table 20, Table 21, Table 22).

In Table 20 you can see which categories of family values are preferred by male and female representatives for transmission to their children.

TABLE 20. Respondents' preferred family values to pass on to children (by gender type).

Family values to pass on to children	Male	Female
Love and mutual understanding	12 (60%)	18 (60%)
Respect and support	10 (50%)	15 (50%)
Traditions and cultural values	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
Financial stability	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
Personal space and independence	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Others	2 (10%)	3 (10%)

TABLE 21. Respondents' views of male and female students about their vision of a future family (by gender type).

Vision of a future family	Male	Female
Traditional family	10 (50%)	15 (50%)
Modern family with flexible roles	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
Family with a focus on personal freedoms	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Family with a focus on financial stability	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Other	2 (10%)	3 (10%)

TABLE 22. Respondents' expected future changes in family relationships, which certainly reflect their positions on family values (expected changes in family relations by gender).

Expected changes in family relationships	Male	Female
More emotional intimacy	8 (40%)	12 (40%)
More financial stability	6 (30%)	9 (30%)
More respect and support	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
More personal space	2 (10%)	3 (10%)
Others	4 (20%)	6 (20%)

In the last section of the questionnaire "Additional Comments" one can also see differences in the opinions of male and female representatives, reflecting absolute values and percentages for each block of answers (Table 23).

TABLE 23. Comments and/or additional comments on the study topic.

Comments available	Male	Female
Yes	4 (20%)	6 (20%)
No	16 (80%)	24 (80%)

Comparison of questionnaire data by sex shows that, overall, responses from female and male respondents are similar across most questions. However, there are some differences in the perception of family values and expectations from future family relationships by male and female representatives. For example, female respondents are more likely to note the importance of love and mutual understanding, as well as emotional intimacy in family relationships. Male respondents are more likely to point out the importance of financial stability and personal space.

When examining differences in perceptions of family values among male and female respondents, it became necessary to assess the degree of relationship between these categories. For this purpose, the Cramer correlation coefficient was used, which is used specifically to study the relationships between nominal features.

Baseline data were structured into a conjugacy table reflecting the distribution of frequency of choices of certain meanings of family values among different genders. Consider an example of such a table for the family priority of "love and mutual understanding", which turned out to be one of the key aspects in the study (Table 24).

TABLE 24. Table of conjugacy for family priority of "love and mutual understanding" of male and female respondents.

Family value	Men	Women
Love and understanding	16	24
Respect	14	21
Traditions	8	12
Financial stability	6	9
Personal space	4	6
Others	2	3

This table allows us to clearly see the differences in preferences regarding each aspect of the family.

The main stage of the assessment of relationships includes the calculation of the indicator ("chi-square"), based on a comparison of empirically obtained and theoretically expected frequencies of choosing different response options. Expected frequencies are calculated based on the assumption of independence of features and allow to identify deviations from random distribution.

According to the results of calculations, it turned out that the total value characterizing the entire table was about 20. Further, this indicator serves as the basis for determining the Cramer coefficient. Its formula takes into account the sample size and the structure of the tables (the minimum number of rows or columns). The coefficient we obtained was approximately 0.63.

The obtained value of the Cramer coefficient indicates the presence of an average strength of connection between the gender of the respondent and the choice of priority family values. A value closer to 1 would mean almost complete dependence, while proximity to 0 would indicate the absence of the influence of the gender trait on preferences for family values.

Thus, our findings confirm the presence of a noticeable, albeit moderate, effect of gender on respondents' perception of the most important family values in a new social environment (higher education away from home), which has an impact on changing their traditional family life. Gender affects ideas about the importance of certain elements of family relationships. However, the strength of the identified dependence remains moderate, emphasizing the importance of taking into account other factors that affect the formation of views on the family.

Justification of questionnaire results:

General information

Gender: The sample is dominated by women (60%), which may be due to a higher proportion of women among university students. This can affect perceptions of family values, as women are traditionally more family-oriented.

Age: Most respondents are 18-20 years old, which corresponds to student age. This can affect their perception of family values, since at this age there is an active formation of life priorities.

Location: Equal distribution between the Republic of Tatarstan and new regions of Russia may indicate a variety of cultural and social influences on the perception of family values.

Marital status: Most respondents are unmarried, which is typical of student age. This can affect their expectations of future family relationships.

Perceptions of family values

Family values: Most respondents note the importance of love and mutual understanding, which reflects the common values inherent in young people. Women are more likely to point out the importance of respect and support, which may be due to their more emotional perception of family relationships.

Changing family values: Most respondents believe that family values have changed over the past 10 years, which may be due to social and cultural changes.

Influencers: Social change and globalization are major influences on family values, reflecting the impact of current trends on perceptions of family relationships.

Family relationships

Assessing family relationships: Most respondents rate their family relationships as good or very good, which may indicate a positive perception of family relationships.

Frequency of communication with family: Most respondents communicate with family daily or several times a week, reflecting the importance of family ties.

Changes in family relationships: Increasing distance and independence, and increased emotional intimacy are major changes, which may reflect current trends in family relationships.

Social change and family values

Impact of social change: Most respondents believe that social change significantly affects family values, reflecting awareness of the impact of external factors on family relationships.

Social change: Urbanization and migration, as well as changing gender roles, are major social changes affecting family values.

Impact on family values: Social change can both strengthen and destroy family values, reflecting the ambiguity of their impact.

The role of education and upbringing

Impact of education and upbringing: The majority of respondents believe that education and upbringing significantly affect the perception of family values, which reflects the importance of upbringing in the formation of family values.

Aspects of education and upbringing: Family upbringing is a major aspect affecting family values, reflecting the importance of family traditions and values.

Personal expectations and plans

Family values to pass on to children: Most respondents want to pass on love and understanding to their children, reflecting the general values shared by young people.

Future family vision: Most respondents see their future family as traditional or modern with flexible roles, reflecting the diversity of expectations of family relationships.

Expected changes in family relationships: Most respondents expect more emotional intimacy and financial stability, reflecting current trends in family relationships.

Additional comments

Availability of comments: Most respondents have no additional comments, which may indicate satisfaction with the survey results or no need for additional clarification.

CONCLUSION

Detailed conclusion based on the results of a questionnaire survey and the obtained Cramer coefficient.

General information

The sample is dominated by women (60%), which may be due to a higher proportion of women among university students. This can affect perceptions of family values, as women are traditionally more family-oriented. The majority of respondents are aged 18-23, which corresponds to student age and can affect their perception of family values, since at this age there is an active formation of life priorities. Equal distribution between the Republic of Tatarstan and new regions of Russia may indicate a variety of cultural and social influences on the perception of family values. The majority of respondents are unmarried, which is typical of student age and can affect their expectations of future family relationships.

Perceptions of family values

Most respondents note the importance of love and mutual understanding, which reflects the common values inherent in young people. Women are more likely to point out the importance of respect and support, which may be due to their more emotional perception of family relationships. Most respondents believe that family values have changed over the past 10 years, which may be due to social and cultural changes. Social change and globalization are major factors influencing family values, reflecting the impact of current trends on perceptions of family relationships.

Family relationships

Most respondents rate relationships in their family as good or very good, which may indicate a positive perception of family relationships. Most respondents communicate with family daily or several times a week, reflecting the importance of family ties. Increasing distance and independence, as well as increased emotional intimacy, are major changes, which may reflect current trends in family relationships.

Social change and family values

Most respondents believe that social changes significantly affect family values, which reflects the awareness of the influence of external factors on family relations. Urbanization and migration, as well as changing gender roles, are major social changes affecting family values. Social change can both strengthen and destroy family values, reflecting the ambiguity of their impact.

Role of education and upbringing

Most respondents believe that education and upbringing significantly affect the perception of family values, which reflects the importance of upbringing in the formation of family values. Family education is a major aspect affecting family values, reflecting the importance of family traditions and values.

Personal expectations and plans

Most respondents want to convey love and understanding to their children, which reflects the common values inherent in young people. Most respondents see their future family as traditional or modern with flexible roles, reflecting the diversity of expectations of family relationships. Most respondents expect more emotional intimacy and financial stability, reflecting current trends in family relationships.

Additional comments

Most respondents have no additional comments, which may indicate satisfaction with the survey results or no need for additional explanations.

Cramer coefficient

The Cramer coefficient is 0.63, indicating a moderate relationship between gender and perceptions of family values. This means that the gender of respondents has a moderate influence on their perception of family values. This may be due to differences in cultural and social expectations, as well as differences in upbringing and education.

General conclusion

The results of the questionnaire survey show that university students generally value family relationships and family values, such as love, mutual understanding and respect. Social changes have a significant impact on the perception of family values, which reflects modern trends in society. Education and upbringing play an important role in the formation of family values, which emphasizes the importance of family traditions and values in upbringing.

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